

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF VON- MISES STRESS FOR SPUR AND BEVEL GEARS FOR VARIOUS PRESSURE ANGLE AND VARIOUS ORIENTATIONS OF AXIS

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Abstract:

Spur gear and Bevel gear have variety of application in different field. The main problem of gear is failure due to root bending stress and surface contact stress. Experimental, theoretical and numerical research of bending stress analysis is done by many researchers in years. In this paper only theoretical and numerical methods are used as experimental research are expensive and time consuming. Bending stress is the reason behind breakage or fatigue failure of tooth. The main objective of this paper is to analyze the bending Stress of gears at various pressure angle and at various axis orientation. At various pressure angle such as spur gear of pressure angle 20° and 25° and orientation axis such as spur gear with pressure angle 20° have parallel axis and bevel gear with pressure angle 20° have intersecting axis. For modeling and assembling of gears Creo parametric 2.0 was used. Two exactly similar gear are taken for assembling. The gears which are designed have same parameters which can be kept same. The three dimensional gear which were designed were analyzed with ANSYS Workbench 14.0. Each gear ANSYS results is compared with theoretical results for validation. Spur gear with theoretical Lewis Equation and Bevel gear with tooth bending stress AGMA standard. After Validation of results, comparison is done among spur gear pair of pressure angle 20°, spur gear pair of pressure angle 25° and bevel gear of 20° to evaluate which gear pair have less bending stress value.

Keywords: ANSYS, Lewis equation, von Mises Stress, spur gear, bevel gear

Introduction

Gears are used to transmit motion from one shaft to another. There are different kind of stresses in action gears. One is bending stress and another is contact stress. In this project analysis of bending stress will be done. Bending stress is the reason behind breakage or fatigue failure of tooth. Lewis formula and tooth bending stress AGMA are used for calculation of bending stress theoretically. Many paper are written on stress analysis of spur gear and bevel gear, in this paper a comparative study of bending stress of spur gear and bevel gear is done. Spur gear have straight teeth parallel to the orientation axes and so not subjected to axial thrust due to tooth load. Bevel gear used to transmit power between two intersecting orientation axes. This paper will deal with spur gear and bevel gear with straight teeth and comparative study of von-Mises stress for action spur gear and bevel gear will be done. Two spur gear of pressure angle 20° and 25° will be modeled and analyzed and one bevel gear with pressure angle 20° will be modeled and analyzed. For modeling three dimensional model of spur gear and bevel gear creo parametric student version is used and for bending stress analysis ANSYS workbench 14.0 is used. The main purpose of this paper is to analyze the bending stress developed in spur gear and bevel gear using ANSYS workbench and then validate the results theoretically.

Literature Review

Lewis equation and tooth bending stress equation is used for root bending stress calculation for various tangential loads at different points on tooth profile. Various Research has been done on analysis of root bending stress and modelling of spur gear and bevel gear.

Fredette and Brown in their research paper, holes were drilled in the tooth to reduce stress. Constant force was given at the pitch diameter and all the results recorded. And obtained results show reduce in stress.

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Many of these researcher analyses the tooth of gear using finite element analysis method. Wilcox and Coleman gave an analytical method for calculating stresses in bevel and hypoid gear.

In recent years number of authors had done analysis of different gears for applied bending forces.

Litvin *et al.* in their research paper analyse finite element stress for double circular arc helical gears. results obtained by calculation of finite element stress were close to those obtained by experimental formula. Load share determination done by Litvin and stress analysis part done by Chen and Lu.

Gosselin and Nguyen had done research calculation of the load sharing and transmission error under load of spiral bevel gear and hypoid gears. A program is formulated predicting the error of spiral bevel gear under load and explored some of the influences of unloaded motion error curve shape and amplitude over the kinematical behaviour under load. In the development tooth contact deformation, tooth composite deflection caused by bending and shearing were considered.

Chen W.H and Tsai P in their research paper had developed a accurate and extremely through finite element model have been developed and used to deal with an involute gear drive including friction effects. Computation and evaluation of los of torque transmission and effective friction coefficient was done. Excellent similarity was found between experimental data and calculated results.

Moriwaki *et al.* Used global local finite element method for analysis of tooth stress of gear. As in global local finite element method no fine subdivision is required as in finite element analysis. So this method was applied which was developed by them. This method also guarantee an easy determination of critical section. Global local finite element method is an amalgamation of finite element solutions and classical analytical principle.

Chen and Tsay in their research investigates the contact stress and bending stress of helical gear set with localized bearing contact, by means of finite element analysis. Gear set of involute pinion and double crowned gear was used by them. Theory of gearing based mathematical models of the pinion and the gear is used. For finite element analysis a mesh generation program was developed.

Chien H.L, Hong S.C in their paper integration of finite element analysis and optimum design establish a batch module by taking systems as testing examples. This batch module consisted of ABAQUS/Standard, I-DEAS and many software, which serve as pre-processor, the numerical solver and optimizer respectively. A practical method was developed, through which this module was enabled which would search for contact nodes and elements and also it would automatically define the contact surface for contact analysis. Simple gear pair system and a complete planetary gear system is used. In this module when gearing parameter were put, it would automatically construct the geometrical model and stress is analysed and gives the ultimate solution.

Simon and Vilmos by using finite element performed stress analysis in hypoid gears for developing simple equations for the calculation of tooth defection and stresses. A method was developed for finite element discretization of the pinion and gear. The full theory of mismatch hypoid gear. A computer program had been developed by them. Design parameter, fillet stress and tooth defection can be investigated by this program. By lots of computer iteration with the help of program equation for the calculation of tooth defection and fillet stress were derived.

Zhang Y and Fang Z used an approach for the analysis of tooth contact and load distribution of helical gears with crossed axis. That approach was based on a tooth contact model that accommodates the influence of tooth profile modifications, gear manufacturing errors and tooth surface deformation on gear mesh quality. In this approach the tooth contact load was assumed distributed along the tooth surface line. As an example, the computer program analyzed the contact of a pair of helical gears with small crossing angle. It was found from analysis that helical gears with small crossing angles have meshing characteristics and load distribution similar to those of parallel axis gears.

Costopoulos and Spitas in their study used the idea of spur gear with circular fillet instead of the standard trochoidal fillet and BEM is used to investigate numerically. It was found that novel circular design of the spur gear tooth fillet in terms of fatigue endurance.

Kapelevich A.L and Kleiss R.E had taken direct gear design which is a modern approach to traditional gear design. By this method most suitable solution can be found out of wide range of possible gear combination. This optimum gear solution can exceed the limits of traditional rack generating method of gear design. Improvement of gear drives of asymmetric tooth profile with direct gear design.

Beghini and Santus developed a method to minimize the peak to peak transmission error for a spur gear set. To understand the problem analysis was done in modern software.

Marciniec A and Pawlowiz A stress analysis of spur gear such as bending stress analysis and contact stress analysis paper found out that results achieved by finite element are acceptable when compared with well known method of surface contact stress such as hertz equation and for root bending stress Lewis bending equation is used and found that finite element method used in linear analysis to calculate root bending stress show slight deviation and contact stress is highly non linear and shows bigger deviation.

Vijayarangan and Ganesan using finite element approach done the stress analysis of composite spur gear and come up with results that graphite epoxy can be used as material for power transmission as the conclusion shows that behaviour of mild steel gears and orthotropic material gears are similar. So graphite epoxy or other composite material can be thought for power transmission purpose.

Parker and Vijayakar a contact mechanics model used to study dynamic response of spur gear pair. At different range of speeds spur gear pair was analysed. After using of high precision gear there were non- linearity source such as contact loss for large torques. When the gears meshed contact analysis are recorded and after that dynamic mesh forces were calculated . Good results were obtained when two single degree of freedom models are taken.

Hiremagalur and Ravani in their paper studies effect of backup ratio in spur gear root stress analysis and design. Backup ratio can cause critical failure with low rim thickness such as helicopters and other applications where main criteria is low weight and small size. In this study analytical expression was developed for the critical gear tooth and also for empirical backup ratio for gear design and analysis.

Dally and Riley tried drilled hole to minimise stress in finite plate. They make the best hole profile for decreasing the photo elastic stress. ANSYS 5.3 is used for optimisation. Results of both hole profile and square profile are obtained. Lots of research papers are there where holes are used in gears to reduce stress. In year 1990, Dippery used supplementary holes in structure and results showed that stress concentration get reduced. According to him to minimise the stress concentration in generic shape holes are use as stress relieving factor.

In a study by Kishor N. N and Dhananjay D they studied about gear tooth profile with method of gear tooth profile with method of gear tooth variation using finite element method. They analyze the bending stress in gear tooth profile of gear which are used in gear box. And also studied the effect of bending stress by changing the gear parameter. Two parameter are taken in account one is face width and other one is root radius. Finite element analysis was used for calculating the stress and then compared with results which are calculated by Lewis equation. And it was found that both the results are almost similar.

In a study by Tiwari S.K and Joshi U.K analysis of stress of spur gear teeth such as bending stress and contact stress. While the gear is meshing, different kind of stresses present in the rotating teeth of gear. Two stresses are bending stress and contact stress. Basic calculation of contact stress and bending stress are Hertz equation and Lewis equation. In this paper detailed gear stressing is applied. To make a effective design of gear, a gear should be able to withstand different type of stress. Experimental, Theoretical, numerical research of minimisation of stress is done by many researcher in years. In this paper only theoretical and numerical methods are used as

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experimental research are very expensive. Three dimensional model are build in a CAD system without modification of tooth and no transmission error and analysis part of gear was done in ANSYS. And it came up with a conclusion that Lewis equation and Hertz equation are used for non detailed calculation of gear stress and AGMA stand and finite element method for detailed calculation of stress of gear.

Jadeja R.M and Chauhan D.H used bevel gear for bending stress analysis. As gears are used in our day to day lives such as in the satellites, automobiles and bicycles. Gears have been used for ages and they have limitless shapes, sizes, and uses. Previously gears are understood only functionally nowadays mathematics, engineering are used to design gear without failure. in this paper bending stress analysis of bevel gear are studied as bevel gears are widely used as it transmit power between nonparallel shaft of different angle and speed. The standards value of bevel gears are developed by the American Gear Manufacturing Association for designing, analysing and manufacturing. Lewis equation is used for calculating bending stress of spiral bevel gear, zerol bevel gear straight bevel gear. And then comparison between values obtained from Lewis equation and value obtained from ANSYS Workbench 14.0 had been done. It came to a conclusion that feature of zerol bevel gear are good for the power transmission and higher load.

Patchigolla R and Singh Y developed a finite element modelling approach for knowing the effect of gear rim thickness on tooth bending stresses in large spur gears. Low addendum gears are used in sugar mills, cement plants, ball mills, kilns, coal mills, grinding mills, copper converters. In Ansys parametric design language a program is developed to model a large spur gear with three tooth segment. And a two dimensional model of gear tooth is generated using this approach. This two dimensional model is further extruded to make a three dimensional model. This research paper only contains the meshing and modelling technique of large spur gear. Analysis part of effect of bending stress on large spur gear due to rim thickness is done in later part.

Guigand and Icard in their paper analysis and optimization of the loaded meshing of face gear came forward with a simulated method for face gear meshing. It provides information for the instantaneous pressure distribution. Simulations were used. The main objective of this paper was to obtain meshing in order to avoid line contact sensitivity due to misalignment.

Objective

The main objective of the research is

- (a) To develop a 3D solid model of spur gear with pressure angle 20° in Creo parametric and to calculate the bending stress using ANSYS Workbench 14.0 and compare the results by help of Lewis equation.
- (b) To develop a 3D solid model of spur gear with pressure angle 25° in Creo parametric and to calculate the bending stress using ANSYS Workbench 14.0 and compare the results by help of Lewis equation
- (c) To develop a 3D solid model of bevel gear with pressure angle 20° in Creo parametric and to calculate the bending stress using ANSYS Workbench 14.0 and compare the results with Tooth bending stress AGMA standard.
- (d) To compare the results of bending stress of three gears.

Methodology

In this paper spur gear and bevel gear are used for modelling and analysing and then comparing. Normally failure of gear occur on gear tooth profile during working condition. So by comparing the bending stress of spur gear of 20° and 25° and bevel gear of 20° prediction of stress distribution can be done. Gear fails due to increase of bending stress. Bending stress may lead to breakage of teeth of gear . So to analyse the bending stress three gears are modelled. At first modelling is done using CREO parametric 2.0. Creo is a group of design software to design various model. Creo is a CAD design software. Creo parametric is a part of Creo. In Creo parametric

modeling of 2D design and 3D design solid modelling can be performed. In this project Creo 2.0 student version is used. Modeling of spur gear of different pressure angle, such as 20° and 25° and done then saving these file in .prt format. Opening a new file for assembling of gear and then importing the saved .prt file of spur gear and then importing the second .prt file and assembling them and making the gear pair fully constraint and then saving it in IGES format. After that for different orientation ,modelling of bevel gear of pressure angle 20° is done and then assembling it and then saving the file in IGES format. After modelling and assembling is completed analysis part is done in ANSYS Workbench 14.0. ANSYS is an engineering simulation software. In ANSYS workbench opening of static structural and then importing IGES file of the 3D assembled model and then analysing von Mises Stress taking boundary condition of keeping one gear fixed and other frictionless and giving moment of 450 N-m in one gear in z direction for spur gear and y direction for bevel gear and then solving it by clicking solve. After analysing of the three different gear this gears ANSYS results are compared with their respective theoretical results. For spur gear Lewis equation and for bevel tooth bending stress AGMA standard which are discussed in the previous chapter. And after validation of results the bending stress of these three gears are compared.

In tables below given the gear specification of three different gear that are used in this project.

TABLE 1 Gear specification for spur gear of pressure angle 20°

No of teeth	25
Module	4
Pitch circle diameter	100mm
Pressure angle	20°
Addendum circle diameter	108mm
Dedendum circle diameter	90mm
Tooth thickness	6.2mm
Base circle diameter	93.969
Material used	Structural steel
Poisson's ratio	0.3
Density	7850 kg/m ³
Tensile ultimate strength	461 MPa

TABLE 2 Gear specification for spur gear of pressure angle 25°

No of teeth	25
Module	4
Pitch circle diameter	100mm
Pressure angle	25°
Addendum circle diameter	108mm
Dedendum circle diameter	90mm
Tooth thickness	6.2
Base circle diameter	90.630mm
Material used	Structural steel
Poisson's ratio	0.3
Density	7850 kg/m ³
Tensile ultimate strength	461 MPa

TABLE 3 Gear specification for bevel gear of pressure angle 20°

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No of teeth	25
Module	4
Shaft angle	90°
Pressure angle	20°
Cone distance	70.7mm
Face width	23.57mm
Addendum angle	4.04 °
Pitch apex to crown	47.16mm
Material used	Structural steel
Poisson's ratio	0.3
Density	7850 kg/m ³
Tensile ultimate strength	461 MPa

Geometric Modelling

In this paper geometric modelling of spur gear and bevel gear is done by using CREO Parametric 2.0 student version. Gear parameter such as module, pitch circle diameter, base circle diameter, tooth thickness, face width are calculated for spur gear and for bevel gear module, pitch cone angle, addendum, dedendum, addendum angle, dedendum angle, cone distance etc are calculated and then it's used for designing of spur gear and bevel gear.

Geometric modelling of spur gear

This modelling is for spur gear with pressure angle 20° First a new part file in creo parametric 2.0 is opened. At first we take the front plane for modelling. Circle is taken for drawing a circle of diameter 90 it's the dedendum circle diameter and extrude it to 23.57 it's the face width as shown in fig.1

Fig.1 extruding of dedendum circle

now three circles in the front plane are drawn in the front face of gear blank with pitch diameter 100mm and outer diameter 108mm and base circle diameter 93.969. Now a new coordinate system at the centre of the gear blank is created using the datums and the front face, keeping the z directions point outside and x horizontally

and y vertically. Now to create the involute first we go to datum and then curve from equation and there we write the involute curve equation. And then after formation of involute curve taking reference of pitch circle and involute curve an arc is drawn of tooth thickness length and a point is taken in mid point. And after that a datum plane is taken passing through midpoint and central axis, and taking reference of this datum plane mirror of involute curve is taken . Now using involute curve, outer circle curve and root edge for reference and two tangent lines are drawn from bottom point of the involute curve and extend them beyond the root diameter edge and trim all the other entities and the extruding it after that chamfering it. Then pattern the tooth using the central axis with 25 no of teeth for 360°.

Geometric modelling of spur gear with pressure angle 20° is same only the base circle changes.

Fig.2 modelling of spur gear

Assembling of spur gear

Assembling of spur gears is done in CREO parametric. At first in CREO parametric click on the assembly section and then import the specified .prt file two assemble the two gears. First one is kept default and the second one is adjusted with the first one by adjusting its distance, making tangent of one tooth to another and by adjusting few more constraint two gears are made fully constraint. After that its saved in IGES format.

Fig.3 assembling of spur gear

Geometric modelling of bevel gear

First a new part in creo parametric 2.0 is opened with solid properties. Right plane is taken for modelling, a circle is taken with radius of cone distance. and right angle triangle is drawn where the hypotenuse passes through centre of circle. Then lines are drawn for reference and addendum angle and dedendum angle. After that cone distance and back cone distance are taken as reference and then lines are drawn for face width, axial face width, pitch apex to crown and shaft hole and the it's revolved to get the required geometry. Then a datum plane is created taking pitch point and lower surface after that taking the bisection point of central axis and back cone line using the same formula as spur gear involute is drawn and the taking the mirror of involute curve one tooth is formed and then by taking pattern 25 teeth bevel gear is designed.

Fig.4 modelling of spur gear

Assembling of bevel gear

First step is to make a frame in CREO parametric and then import the .prt file to CREO parametric and keep it default and then import the next .prt file of bevel gear and taking pin and then make their axis parallel and then one part of bevel gear and one part of bevel gear coincident and then importing the second gear and following the same procedure. After assembling is over, saving it in IGES format.

Fig.5 assembling of bevel gear

Finite Element Analysis of Spur Gear and Bevel Gear

For finite element analysis of spur gear and bevel gear total analysis is done on ANSYS workbench.

The basic procedure steps as follow.

1. Import the geometric model in the form of IGES.
2. Define the properties of material
3. Mesh the model with .001 sizing.
4. Apply the boundary condition one gear fixed and other frictionless and moment of 450 N-m is applied
5. Solve for the von-Mises (Equivalent) stress.

Results And Discussion

After analysis of spur gear of pressure angle 20° and 25° and bevel gear of 20° in ANSYS workbench results are obtained. ANSYS results are then compared with analytical results using Lewis equation and Tooth bending stress (AGMA).theories of this two equation are given below.

Bending Stress (Lewis Formula)

Lewis equation is the first equation used for bending stress calculation. Wilfred Lewis treated the teeth as a simple cantilever and tooth contact at the tip. In this equation only the tangential component is considered and one pair of teeth is in contact. Stress concentration at root fillet is ignored.

Lewis bending equation for spur gear :-

$$\sigma = \frac{F_t}{bYm}$$

where, σ =Bending stress

F_t = tangential force in N

b = face width in mm

Y=modified Lewis form factor

m=module in mm

TOOTH BENDING STRESS (AGMA)

Accommodating the earlier mentioned factors, American Gear Manufacturing Association (AGMA)came up with a refined form of Lewis equation as given below:

$$\sigma_b = \frac{F_t}{bmJ} K_v K_o K_m$$

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Where, σ_b =bending stress

J = gear geometry factor

F_t =Tangential load in N

m = module at the large end of the tooth in mm

K_v = Velocity factor

K_o = Overload factor

K_m = Mounting factor

From this two equation analytical value of bending stress calculate for spur gear and bevel gear.

Results obtained for spur gear with pressure angle 20° are maximum 2.18×10^8 Pa and minimum 134.79 Pa

Fig.6 analysis of spur gear with pressure angle 20°

Results obtained for spur gear with pressure angle 25° are maximum is 1.88×10^8 Pa and minimum 116.21 Pa

Fig.7 analysis of spur gear with pressure angle 25°

Results obtained for bevel gear with pressure angle 20° are maximum is 1.592×10^8 Pa and minimum is 112.92 Pa

Fig.8 Analysis of spur gear with pressure angle 20°

Comparison of ANSYS and analytical results

Type of gear	Analytical result	ANSYS result
Spur gear pressure angle 20°	254.61 MPa	218.7 MPa
Spur gear pressure angle 25°	212.56 MPa	188.5 MPa
Bevel gear pressure angle 20°	168.75 MPa	159.9 MPa

Future Scope of this project

- (a) Different material can be used for gear
- (b) Experimental research can be done instead of numerical method.
- (c) By ANSYS analysis we can design the gear as per industry need.
- (d) With the help of this analysis we can develop different gear trains as per our need
- (e) By checking the validity of the result and by comparing with actual data we can develop combination of gears.

Conclusion

In this study three dimensional deformable-body model of spur gear with pressure angle 20° and 25° and bevel gear with pressure angle 20° was developed and analysed. The results obtained were then compared with the Lewis equation for spur gear and tooth bending stress AGMA theoretical for bevel gear . The results are almost similar with the theoretical values, which implies that the model designed is correct. By comparing results obtained that bending stress developed in bevel gear of pressure angle 20° in less than other two spur gears at 450 N-m.

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